

DIDACTIC PARAMETERS OF THE PIRLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

X.Q.Asrorov

Bukhara State University

Abstract: The article analyzes such strategic tasks as systematic monitoring of the implementation of the international assessment program PIRLS in the educational process, popularization of best practices, and determining the level of assimilation of educational materials by primary school students.

Keywords: PIRLS, educational process, systematic monitoring, best practices, primary school, assessment process, government requirements, achievement levels, strategic objective.

In order to improve the quality and efficiency of education, it is important to study foreign advanced practices and implement the requirements of international standards. In this regard, the adoption of a government resolution on the organization of international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system on the basis of fundamental reforms being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the establishment of cooperation with such an influential organization as the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievements (IEA), can be cited as an example.

The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of December 8, 2018 No. 997 “On the organization of international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system” was adopted. In accordance with the resolution, international studies were organized on the following international assessment programs:

- 1) Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study (PIRLS) - assessing the level of reading and comprehension of text by 4th grade primary school students;,
- 2) Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) - assessing the level of mastery of mathematics and natural sciences by 4th and 8th grade students;
- 3) The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) - assessing the level of literacy of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-76 dated May 5, 2025 “On additional measures to ensure the quality of education and improve the system of providing educational services” sets the following priority tasks:

- Introduction of a system for assessing educational and research processes in educational organizations based on international standards;
- Assessing the knowledge and skills of graduates of educational institutions and studying their compliance with the requirements of the modern labor market;
- Developing and improving criteria and methods for assessing the quality of education, taking into account international standards and advanced foreign experience;
- Expanding international relations in the field of ensuring the quality of education, becoming a member of international organizations in the field of quality assessment and ensuring the international recognition of the national accreditation system;
- Conducting scientific research aimed at developing and implementing innovative methods for developing the level of literacy in reading, mathematics and natural sciences in the education system;
- Establishing international relations in the field of assessing the quality of education, developing and implementing international projects, and participating in the organization and holding of international scientific conferences and symposiums;
- Ensuring the successful participation of secondary education institutions in international research;
- Strategic tasks have been set, such as conducting systematic monitoring of the implementation of international assessment programs in the educational process, popularizing best practices in this area, and participating in the development of recommendations and guidelines for educational institutions based on them. From this point of view, in international practice, the following are paid attention to when assessing the knowledge, skills, and qualifications acquired by students:
 - to reflect the acquired knowledge in familiar situations and in their own minds;
 - to ensure that they can apply the acquired knowledge in familiar situations according to the given example;
 - to achieve the ability to transfer the acquired knowledge to new, unfamiliar situations;

Taking into account the above, let's dwell on the assessment systems used in international experience:

PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading and comprehension levels of primary school students in different countries. The study is conducted periodically - once every five years and has been conducted five times so far: in 2001, 2006, 2011, 2016 and 2021. It is a program for assessing the level of reading and comprehension of text in primary school students, and is one of the most

prestigious studies in the field of international assessment. To date, based on the results of the PIRLS international study, participating countries have been implementing various changes and new approaches in their education systems. In most cases, these reforms have yielded positive results. In an era of rapid development, comprehensive support for the creative ideas and creativity of young people, who are the successors of our future, and assessment of their knowledge, skills and competencies based on international criteria and requirements are one of the urgent issues of today.

PIRLS provides an opportunity to make evidence-based decisions to improve reading education. Countries use PIRLS for the following purposes:

- monitoring trends in achievements at the level of education systems on a global scale;
- monitoring the impact of new or revised education policies;
- identifying weaknesses in education and implementing educational reforms;
- improving teaching and learning through research and analysis of PIRLS data;
- monitoring equity or assessing students in additional classes;
- studying reading and teaching.

The PIRLS project was created under the auspices of the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement. Boston College is responsible for organizing the international survey. The preparation of the tasks for the international survey is carried out at the data center in Hamburg. The international PIRLS survey provides an international comparison of data on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students, which can serve as an analysis of public education policies to improve reading and teaching. According to the current definition of PIRLS, reading literacy is the ability to understand and use written language forms that are required by society and valued by the individual, as well as the ability to make sense of texts in different forms. The main focus of the survey is on demonstrating understanding and how to apply acquired knowledge to new projects and situations. The learner is an active participant in this process, creating meaning, observing the text, and consciously choosing and applying effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows a set of rules and patterns that help the learner interpret the text. Any text can take many forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents, and newspapers, as well as digital written forms.

The PIRLS study assesses two types of reading that students do during school and outside of school:

1. Reading to assess the learner's literary experience;

2. Reading to acquire and use information.

According to the study's rules, four groups of reading skills are assessed when reading literary and informational texts:

- finding specific information;
- drawing inferences;
- interpreting and synthesizing information;
- analyzing and evaluating content, language features, and text structure.

PIRLS tests are available in four levels, each with a different format: Level 1 tests assess a student's knowledge, skills, and abilities based on information provided by the teacher. Tests are administered based on clearly defined algorithms;

Level 2 tests are tests that require comparison and comparison. Tests that can be based on the information provided by the teacher;

Level 3 tests are tests that require finding the necessary information from several sources, comparing and contrasting them, and finding the most appropriate solution.

In the PIRLS study, the levels of reading literacy are described as follows:

- The highest level (625 points and above) - Students can master the text as a whole and at the same time understand its individual parts in relation to each other. They can rely on the text to justify their opinion when explaining the author's idea.
- High level (550 points) - Students understand the important messages of the text, draw their own conclusions based on the text, can evaluate both the content and form of the text, and pay attention to some of its linguistic features.
- Medium level (475 points) – Students can find information in the text, draw their own conclusions based on the text, using some features of the text form and language.
- Low level (400 points) – Students can distinguish clearly presented and easily limited information in the text.

The following system is used for qualitative and quantitative assessment of the work performed in PIRLS:

- correct answers in the multiple choice method are scored 1 point;
- correct answers in determining the sequence of the topic are scored 1 point;
- tasks requiring a free answer are scored from 1 to 3 points, depending on the complexity of the task.

The main important factor in the implementation of the international assessment program PIRLS in the public education system is the implementation of the PIRLS in practice. When assessing the level of development of reading and comprehension skills of primary school students based on the PIRLS international assessment programs, it is important to choose optimal intensive forms and methods in the

educational process, and to use modern information resources purposefully. The practical application of the international assessment program PIRLS will serve as the basis for the quality of education in our country and the creation of a national assessment system in accordance with international standards.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2018 yil 8 dekabrda "Xalq ta'limi tizimida ta'lim sifatini baholash sohasida xalqaro tadqiqotlarni tashkil etish to'g'risida"gi 997-sonli qarori.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 yil 29 apreldagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasi xalq ta'limi tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi PF-5712-son.
3. Шляйхер Андреас. Образование мирового уровня. Как встроить школьную систему XXI века. Москва: Издательство «Национальное образование», 2019. – 336 с.
4. Гладкая, И. В. Оценка образовательных результатов школьников Текст. : учеб.-метод. пособие для учителей / И. В. Гладкая; под ред. А. П. Тряпицыной. СПб.: КАРО, 2008. - 144 с.
5. Чернявская А.П., Гречин, Б.С. Современные средства оценивания результатов обучения// Учебно-методическое пособие. – Ярославль: Изд-во ЯГПУ. 2008.
6. Абрамова, Н.С. Гладкова, М.Н. Ваганова. О.И. Особенности разработки оценочных материалов в условиях реализации компетентностного подхода // Проблемы современного педагогического образования. – М., 2017. №57-1.